

The farnesoid X receptor (FXR) antagonist 7β-isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid improves glucose metabolism in mice on a Western diet

Alzbeta Stefela^{a,b}, Klara Dohnalova^{c,d}, Hana Lastuvkova^e, Josef Skoda^a, Maria Bajnokova^a, Sophie Lestavel^f, Veronique Touche^f, Miroslav Kaspar^g, Eva Kudova^g, Milos Hroch^h, Stanislav Micuda^e, Otto Kucera^b, Petr Pavek^{a,*}

^a Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

^b Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

^c Czech Centre for Phenogenomics, Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

^d 1st Medical Faculty, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

^e Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

^f University Lille, Inserm, CHU Lille, Institut Pasteur de Lille, U1011-EGID, Lille F-59000, France

^g Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic

^h Department of Medical Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Farnesoid X receptor antagonist
TGR5
Glucagon-like peptide 1
Glucose transporters

ABSTRACT

The significant roles of the farnesoid X receptor (FXR) and Takeda G protein-coupled receptor 5 (TGR5) in regulating metabolic pathways have recently been demonstrated. However, the precise effects of FXR inhibitors on glucose metabolism remain to be elucidated. In this study, we examined the impact of 7β-isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid (7β-ipCDCA), a dual FXR antagonist and TGR5 agonist, on impaired glucose metabolism in mice fed a Western diet. The dual FXR antagonistic/TGR5 agonistic activity of 7β-ipCDCA was confirmed through gene reporter assays. We evaluated its effects on glucose homeostasis using a glucose tolerance test in C57BL/6 mice fed a Western diet supplemented with sugar in drinking water for 24 weeks. The glucose-lowering mechanism was further investigated by measuring GLP-1 release, mRNA expression of glucose transporters, and relevant genes involved in glucose metabolism in intestinal, hepatic, white adipose, and kidney tissues, and in human NCI-H716 and murine GLUTag L cell lines. Additionally, bile acid metabolome and hepatic lipidome analyses were conducted. Results showed that 7β-ipCDCA improves glucose homeostasis altered by a Western diet in mice via enhanced GLP-1 secretion and decreased expression of glucose transporters in the ileum

Abbreviations: 7β-ipCDCA, 7β-isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid; ACACA, acetyl-CoA carboxylase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; BA, bile acid; BAAT, bile acid-CoA:amino acid N-acyltransferase; BSEP, bile-salt export pump; CAR, constitutive androstane receptor; CD36, cluster of differentiation 36, fatty acid translocase; CDCA, chenodeoxycholic acid; CE, cholesteryl ester; Cer, ceramide; CPT1A, carnitine palmitoyltransferase I; CRE, cAMP response element-binding; CYP27A1, sterol 27-hydroxylase; CYP2C70, cytochrome P450 monooxygenase 2C70; CYP7A1, cholesterol 7α-hydroxylase; CYP7B1, 25-hydroxycholesterol 7-α-hydroxylase; CYP8B1, sterol 12-α-hydroxylase; DG, diacylglycerol; DPP-4, dipeptidyl peptidase-4; ELISA, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; FASN, fatty acid synthetase; FGF15, fibroblast growth factor 15; FSK, forskolin; FXR, farnesoid X receptor; G6PC, glucose-6-phosphatase; GCK, glucokinase; GLP-1, glucagon-like peptide 1; GLUT, glucose transporter; GPBAR1, G protein-coupled bile acid receptor 1; GR, glucocorticoid receptor; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; HFD, high fat diet; HOMA-IR, homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance; LCA, lithocholic acid; LC-MS, liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; LPC, lysophosphatidylcholine; LXR, liver X receptor; MASH, metabolic dysfunction–associated steatohepatitis formerly non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, NASH; MC, methylcellulose; MCA, muricholic acid; MRP, multidrug resistant protein; NTCP, Na⁺ taurocholate cotransport peptide; OCA, obeticholic acid; OSTα/β, organic solute transporter α/β; PC, phosphatidylcholine; PCK1, phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase 1; PDK4, pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase; PGC1A, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-α; PLIN2, perilipin 2; PPAR, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor; PS, phosphatidylserine; PXR, pregnane X receptor; RT-qPCR, real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction; SCD1, stearoyl-CoA desaturase; SGLT, sodium-glucose linked transporter; SHP, small heterodimer partner; SM, sphingomyelin; SREBF1, sterol regulatory element-binding transcription factor 1; T2DM, type 2 diabetes mellitus; TβMCA, tauro-beta-muricholic acid; TCA, taurocholic acid; TGR5, Takeda G protein-coupled receptor 5; TR, thyroid hormone receptor; VDR, vitamin D receptor.

* Correspondence to: Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Heyrovského 1203, Hradec Kralove 500 03, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: pavek@faf.cuni.cz (P. Pavek).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2025.107950>

Received 7 May 2025; Received in revised form 22 August 2025; Accepted 9 September 2025

Available online 11 September 2025

1043-6618/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

and kidneys. While its impact on liver function was marginal, 7 β -ipCDCA increased plasma taurocholic acid levels. Furthermore, 7 β -ipCDCA elevated hepatic triacylglycerols in mice on a chow diet, whereas mice on the Western diet were protected from triacylglycerol accumulation. This study highlights the role of FXR in regulating intestinal glucose transporters and GLP-1 secretion, emphasizing the therapeutic potential of combined FXR antagonists/TGR5 agonists in managing hyperglycemia.

1. Introduction

The nuclear receptor Farnesoid X receptor (FXR) is a key regulator of bile acids (BAs) homeostasis in the enterohepatic cycle. FXR activation suppresses the expression of cholesterol 7 α -hydroxylase (CYP7A1), a rate-limiting enzyme in hepatic BA synthesis, by inducing the expression of small heterodimer partner (SHP) in the liver and fibroblast growth factor 15 (FGF15) in the small intestine [1,2].

The role of FXR in the regulation of glucose homeostasis is complex. Whole-body FXR-knockout (FXR-KO) mice exhibited elevated plasma glucose levels and impaired insulin sensitivity [3]. However, when challenged with a high-fat diet (HFD), FXR-deficient animals failed to develop obesity and showed improved glucose homeostasis compared to wild-type animals [4,5]. Interestingly, intestinal-specific FXR-KO mice did not develop obesity or metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH)-like phenotype under HFD [6,7]. In contrast, a similar protective effect was not observed in liver-specific FXR-KO mice [4]. Consistently, the expression of gluconeogenic genes was attenuated in the liver of mice treated with FXR agonists such as GW4064, administered intraperitoneally [8]. Nevertheless, oral administration of an FXR agonist led to hyperglycaemia in HFD-fed mice [9]. These findings underscore the distinct roles of hepatic and intestinal FXR signaling, as well as the influence of nutritional status on glucose homeostasis in the presence of FXR agonists. Specifically, hepatic FXR activation combined with intestinal FXR inhibition during excessive nutrient intake (such as an HFD or Western diet) appears to exert a protective effect against disrupted glucose metabolism.

Recent studies have shown that the FXR antagonist tauro- β -muricholic acid (T β MCA) can improve glucose metabolism by inhibiting intestinal FXR signalling [6,10]. T β MCA is a primary bile acid (BA), and the composition of the BA pool appears to have a significant impact on metabolic regulation. For instance, metformin, the first-line therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), restores metabolic function, including the reduction of hyperglycaemia, by increasing intestinal concentrations of glycoconjugated bile acids, a BA with FXR antagonistic properties, in humans [11]. Similarly, the BA sequestrant colestevlam exhibits anti-diabetic properties by inhibiting intestinal FXR activity and enhancing glucose clearance in peripheral tissues in diabetic mice [12].

Recent research has identified several FXR antagonists that ameliorate altered glucose metabolism. A triterpenoid F6 derived from betulinic acid has been shown to improve MASH progression, including glucose sensitivity, in a murine model of MASH by inhibiting intestinal FXR signalling [13]. Additionally, sesamin, an active lignan isolated from sesame oil, and its metabolites reduced blood glucose levels in mice while acting as FXR antagonists [14]. Other selective FXR antagonists, including mebhdyrolin [15], oleanolic acid alkyl ester derivatives [16], and compound HS218 [17], have also been shown to decrease hyperglycaemia in diabetic mouse models by suppressing gluconeogenesis in the liver.

Inhibition of intestinal FXR has been shown to promote the release of glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) [18,19]. GLP-1 is an incretin secreted by enteroendocrine L-cells that enhances postprandial insulin secretion from the pancreas in response to glucose [20]. Targeting GLP-1 represents an appealing strategy for managing type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Indeed, GLP-1 analogues or inhibitors of GLP-1 degradation, such as dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, represent current anti-diabetic medications with additional positive effects on weight loss [21]. Importantly, GLP-1 has been shown to improve glucose

metabolism in MASH [22,23]. Furthermore, increased GLP-1 secretion via BA-mediated FXR antagonism has been proposed as a mechanism underlying the beneficial effects of hepatic thyroid hormone signalling on glucose metabolism [24].

Besides FXR, another BA receptor, Takeda G protein-coupled receptor 5 (TGR5, also known as G protein-coupled bile acid receptor 1, GPBAR1), is involved in the regulation of GLP-1 secretion from enteroendocrine L cells [22,25]. TGR5 is widely expressed in various organs, including the small intestine, stomach, liver, spleen, and gallbladder. Robust correlations between TGR5 activity and metabolic regulation, including glucose homeostasis, have been established in recent studies [26]. Insulin and GLP-1 secretion levels, as well as glucose tolerance, were markedly elevated by TGR5 overexpression in mice [27,28]. Treatment with TGR5 agonists significantly improved blood glucose levels in diabetic [29], insulin-resistant [30], and MASH mouse models [31] and in obese rats [32]. Notably, these beneficial effects were not observed in TGR5-deficient animals, indicating that TGR5 plays an active role in the pathophysiology of T2DM [33]. Additional studies have associated the positive effects on glucose homeostasis with an increased activation of TGR5 by BAs [7,34–38].

Glucose absorption from the small intestine is tightly linked to plasma glucose levels and mediated by two main glucose transporters: the apical sodium-glucose linked transporter 1 (SGLT1, Slc5a1) and the basolateral glucose transporter 2 (GLUT2, Slc2a2). When glucose concentrations in the intestinal lumen are high, the GLUT2 transporter is rapidly inserted into the apical membrane of enterocytes, facilitating glucose diffusion [39–41]. Insulin resistance has been reported to impair GLUT2 trafficking capacity, resulting in the constant high-level expression of GLUT2 in the brush border membrane of enterocytes [42,43]. Additionally, the expression and activity of SGLT1 are increased in diabetes, implying it might represent a promising pharmacological target [44–48]. In the proximal tubule of the nephron, another member of the SGLT family, SGLT2, regulates renal glucose reabsorption. SGLT2 inhibitors, commonly referred to as gliflozins, represent the first-line treatment of T2DM. Surprisingly, the effect of FXR on glucose transporters remains poorly investigated. The only reports suggest that the downregulation of GLUT2 was associated with the FXR inhibition in human renal HK-2 cells [49]. In another study, BAs increased GLUT2 expression via the FXR-S1PR2-ERK1/2 pathway, and this effect was abolished by FXR antagonist Z-guggulsterone [50].

Here, we present a BA derivative, 7 β -isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid (7 β -ipCDCA), with combined FXR antagonistic and TGR5 agonistic properties that efficiently restored glucose tolerance in mice on a Western diet. In addition, we investigated its mechanism of action, revealing increased GLP-1 secretion and decreased expression of glucose transporters in the intestine. Notably, the hepatic lipid metabolism and plasmatic BAs pool had a marginal effect on glucose metabolism regulation by 7 β -ipCDCA.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Drugs

7 β -isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid (7 β -ipCDCA, Fig. 1a) has been recently discovered by our team, and it was synthesized as described previously [51]. Obeticholic acid (OCA) was purchased from MedChemExpress. Litcholic acid (LCA) and forskolin (FSK) were obtained from Merck.

2.2. Mouse models

The EU Directive 2010/63/EU was implemented in all animal experiments. The care of all animals strictly followed the guidelines established by the Animal Welfare Body of the Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové. The animal trials were agreed by the Animal Welfare Body of the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports (approval No. MSMT-31682/2022–3). Male mice were chosen because of their higher susceptibility to diet-induced metabolic dysfunction [52].

Six-week-old C57BL/6 male mice were purchased from Velaz (Prague, Czech Republic) and underwent a 7-day acclimatisation period. Subsequently, mice were randomly separated into 2 groups of 20–22 animals. Control group (C) received chow diet (PicoLab® RD 20, LabDiet) and tap water, the other group was fed a Western diet (WD, W, AIN-76A WD, TestDiet, St. Louis, MO, USA) where 40 % of calories originated from saturated fat (milk fat), 0.2 % cholesterol, 15.4 % from protein (casein), and 44.5 % from carbohydrates (sucrose). In addition, glucose (18.1 g/l) and fructose (24 g/l) were added to drinking water for 24 weeks. Six weeks prior to the sacrifice, both dietary groups were randomly divided to receive either 7 β -ipCDCA 10 mg/kg/d or vehicle

(1 % methylcellulose, MC) by oral gavage once daily concurrently with the respective diets (Fig. 1d). The dose and frequency of 10 mg/kg/d 7 β -ipCDCA were selected based on preliminary pharmacokinetic experiments, ensuring the effective biological response and avoiding toxicity or undesirable side effects. Groups are assigned as follows: C for the vehicle-treated group on the chow diet (n = 10 animals), C+7 β ip for the 7 β -ipCDCA-treated group on the chow diet (n = 8), W for the vehicle-treated group on WD (n = 9), W+7 β ip for the 7 β -ipCDCA-treated group on WD (n = 10). One mouse from the cohort on WD started losing weight after 7 weeks on WD and was excluded from the study.

In the case of the experiments with a two-week treatment period, seven-week-old C57BL/6 male mice received WD (as described above) for 24 weeks. Two weeks before the sacrifice, mice were separated into three groups (n = 8) to receive vehicle (WD, 1 %MC), 7 β -ipCDCA (W+7 β ip, 10 mg/kg/d), and OCA (W+OCA, 10 mg/kg/d). One week prior to the sacrifice, the intraperitoneal glucose tolerance tests (ipGTT) were performed as described below. After the administration of the last dose of tested compounds or vehicle, the mice were placed in the metabolic cages, and stool was collected for 24 h. The mice were then anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of pentobarbital (50 mg/kg),

Fig. 1. 7 β -isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid (7 β -ipCDCA) is a potent combined Fxr antagonist and TGR5 agonist. (a) Structure of 7 β -ipCDCA, (b) 7 β -ipCDCA inhibits murine Fxr activation by 1 μ M obeticholic acid (OCA) in HepG2 cells co-transfected with FXRE-luc luciferase, RXR α , and murine Fxr expression vectors. (c) 7 β -ipCDCA activates TGR5 in HepG2 cells co-transfected with CRE-luc and TGR5 expression vector. Data were normalized to *Renilla* luciferase activity and are expressed relative to those of vehicle-treated cells. Values are presented as means \pm SD of three independent experiments performed in biological triplicates (n = 3). IC₅₀ and EC₅₀ values were calculated using concentration-response curves nonlinear fitting in GraphPad software. (d) The proof-of-concept study design. (e–h) Body weight, liver weight, and plasma transaminases (ALT, AST) levels were determined in mice fed Western (W) and chow (C) diets for 24 weeks and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (7 β ip, 10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) for the last 6 weeks. Data are presented as means \pm SD with individual values superimposed on the graph (n = 8–10 mice per group). **P < 0.01, ****P < 0.0001 vs. vehicle-treated mice on chow diet (C).

and bile was collected for 45 min through the cannulated gallbladder [53]. At the end of the experiment, a blood sample was taken from the *inferior vena cava*, the mice were sacrificed by anaesthesia, and their organs were excised and immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen. Plasma samples were obtained from the whole blood by centrifugation at 2000 g for five minutes at 4 °C. Samples were stored at -80 °C until analysis.

2.3. Biochemical analysis

Liver enzymes (ALT, AST, ALP) were measured in whole blood using a commercial Preventive Care Profile Plus test with a Vetscan 2 device (Abaxis, Union City, CA). Plasma triacylglycerols (TG) and cholesterol (total, HDL, and LDL) were analysed on an AU480 biochemistry analyzer (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA).

2.4. Bile acids metabolome

The concentration and individual BAs in plasma, bile, and stool were measured using a published liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) method [54]. Samples were prepared as described previously [55].

2.5. Glucose tolerance test, HOMA-IR calculation

Prior to the glucose tolerance test, mice were fasted overnight. The next day, blood glucose was measured from the tail at time points: t = 0, 15, 30, 60, and 120 min after intraperitoneal glucose (1.0 mg/kg) injection. At time t = 0, blood was sampled to measure insulin plasma concentration by ELISA (Alpco, Salem, NH). HOMA-IR was calculated using the formula: fasting insulin ($\mu\text{U/L}$) x fasting glucose (mmol/L)/22.5.

2.6. GLP-1 determination

Active GLP-1 was determined in 26-week-old C57BL/6 mice that were on a Western or chow diet for the last 20 weeks. 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg) was distributed to mice for 7 days before the GLP-1 determination. On the day of the blood sampling, mice were fasted for 5 h prior to the sitagliptin administration (25 mg/kg, Merck) via oral gavage [56]. After 45 min, the gavage of glucose (2 g/kg) followed. After 15 min, blood was collected by retro-orbital venipuncture under isoflurane anaesthesia in EDTA-coated tubes containing DPP-4 inhibitor Diprotin A (Merck). GLP-1 active and total GLP-1 were determined with commercial ELISA kits (Alpco and Millipore, respectively).

In the differentiated NCI-H716 cells, GLP-1 was determined after serum starvation as described previously [51]. Briefly, cells were incubated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 μM) in Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) supplemented with 0.2 % (w/v) BSA and 50 μM Diprotin A for 2 h. GLP-1 was determined by ELISA (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany). Data were normalized to protein concentration, and they are presented as a fold protein increase after FXR ligand treatment compared to control (vehicle, 0.1 % DMSO-treated) samples.

2.7. Real-time quantitative PCR

The RNA was isolated from homogenized samples by the phenol/chloroform method with TRI-reagent (Merck) according to the manufacturer's protocol as described [57]. The excessive lipid content from adipose tissue cuts was removed with centrifugation of the homogenized samples at 4 °C, 12,000 g for 10 min prior to RNA isolation. The cDNA was synthesized using a RevertAid RT Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific), and RT-qPCR was run in the Quant Studio 6 instrument using the Fast Advanced Master Mix (ThermoFisher Scientific). All the probes (ThermoFisher Scientific) are listed in the table (Supplementary material, Table T1). Data were normalized to Rplp0 and β -actin as reference genes, evaluated by the $\Delta\Delta\text{C}_q$ method according to MIQE guidelines,

and are presented as fold change to control samples (vehicle-treated cohort on a chow diet).

2.8. Lipidome analysis

Materials for lipidome analysis, LC-MS-grade solvents, and modifiers were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA): methanol, water, methyl tert-butyl ether, 2-propanol (IPA), acetonitrile, ammonium formate, and formic acid. Splash Lipidomix Mass Spec Standard containing, among others, standards of phosphatidylcholine (PC) 15:0_18:1 (d7), phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) 15:0_18:1 (d7), phosphatidylserine (PS) 15:0_18:1 (d7), lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC) 18:1 (d7), lysophosphatidylethanolamine (LPE) 18:1 (d7), cholesterol ester (CE) 18:1 (d7), diglyceride (DG) 15:0_18:1 (d7), triacylglycerol (TG) 15:0_18:1 (d7)_15:0 and sphingomyelin (SM) 18:1_18:1 (d9) was acquired from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, USA). PC 14:0_14:0, PC 22:0_22:0, PC 22:1_22:1, Cer 18:1;2/17:0, TG 16:0_18:0_16:0 (d5), and TG 14:0_16:1_14:0 (d5) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, USA).

To analyse liver samples by mass spectrometry, 225 μL of ice-cold methanol containing lipid standards together with pre-cooled steel beads were added to 12 mg (chow diet) or 10 mg (WD) of the liver tissue. Samples were homogenized using TissueLyser II (30 Hz, 2 x 30 s) (Qiagen). Then, 750 μL of ice-cold methyl tert-butyl ether was added. Samples were vortexed and incubated for 30 min on a rotating wheel. Next, 188 μL of LC-MS-grade water was added, and after vortexing, short incubation, and centrifugation (14000 g, 4 °C), the upper organic phase containing lipids was collected. The organic phase was evaporated using a N₂ concentrator (45 °C) and reconstituted in MeOH/IPA (1/1, v/v). A pooled sample prepared by mixing equal parts of all measured samples was used for quality control and iterative MS/MS measurement.

The 6564 Dual AJS ESI Q-TOF mass spectrometer coupled with 1290 Infinity II LC System (both Agilent) was used to perform analysis of the samples. Chromatographic separation was performed on Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column (130 Å, 1.7 μm , 2.1 mm x 150 mm) (Waters) at 55 °C using gradient of ACN/water (A, 60/40, v/v, with 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1 % formic acid) and 2-propanol/ACN (B, 90/10, v/v, with 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1 % formic acid): 0 min, 20 % B; 3 min, 30 % B; 4.65 min, 43 % B; 5.5 min, 50 % B; 5.6 min, 57 % B; 13.2 min, 70 % B; 23 min, 82.5 % B; 24.5 min, 99 % B; 26 min, 99 % B; 26.1 min, 20 % B; 27 min, 20 % B; plus 13 min of post-run equilibration. The flow rate was set to 0.35 ml/min, and the injection volume was 2 μL . MS conditions: drying gas 8 l/min at 300 °C, nebulizer pressure 35 psi, capillary voltage 3500 V. MS scans were collected in 100–1000 m/z range in positive ESI mode at 1.5 spectra per second. Auto MS2 parameters: collision energy 20 V, acquisition rate was 6 spectra per second. A tuning mix (Agilent) was used for instrument calibration. Peaks from MS measurement were assigned using mass and retention time (RT) information from the lipid library created based on iterative MS2 measurement. MS2 data were processed in MassHunter Lipid Annotator (1.0.54.0) (Agilent). MS data were processed in MassHunter Quantitative Analysis (10.1.733.0) (Agilent).

2.9. Transcriptome analysis

Total RNA from liver homogenates was isolated using the phenol/chloroform method with TRI-reagent (Merck). The samples were further processed as described previously [58]. Briefly, the RNA integrity was measured using the 2100 Bioanalyzer System with Total RNA Nano Chip (Agilent Technologies) (RIN > 7) and for library construction, 520 ng of RNA was quantified using Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer with Qubit RNA BR Assay Kit (Invitrogen). Libraries were constructed with NEBNext Ultra II Directional RNA Library Prep Kit for Illumina (New England Biolabs Inc., Ipswich, MA, USA) and sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq6000 platform (Illumina). Fastq was aligned to the mouse genome (mm10) and quantified using feature Counts. DESeq2 was used to detect differentially expressed genes [59]. A heatmap was generated using z-score

normalized reads ($z = [x - \text{mean}] / \text{standard deviation}$) and visualized with the R package pheatmap. Hierarchical clustering was conducted using the Ward method within the pheatmap R package. The data presented in this publication have been deposited in the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus database under the GEO Series accession number GSE291059.

2.10. Cell culture

Human hepatocellular carcinoma HepG2 cells (ECACC, passage 4–10 after defreezing) were cultivated in antibiotic-free Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Merck), supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1 % L-glutamine, and 1 % sodium pyruvate. Human enteroendocrine colon cancer NCI-H716 cells (ATCC-CCL-251, ECACC, passage 6–8 after defreezing) were maintained in antibiotic-free RPMI-1640 medium, supplemented with 10 % FBS. For each experiment, the NCI-H716 cells were seeded onto 96-well Matrigel (Corning®) coated plates (1×10^5 cells/well) and differentiated for 48 h. GLUTag (passage 3–8 after defreezing) cells were grown in DMEM with 10 % FBS added. Dr. Daniel J. Drucker (Lunenfeld Tanenbaum Research Institute Mt. Sinai Hospital, Toronto) approved Dr. Colette Roche (Centre de Recherche en Cancérologie de Lyon, INSERM U1052, Lyon, France) to generously donate GLUTag cells [55].

2.11. Transient transfection and luciferase gene reporter assays

HepG2 cells were seeded at a density of 40,000 cells/cm² for transient transfection. To determine GPBAR1 activation, cells were transfected with 200 ng of CRE luciferase reporter vector (pGL4.29[luc2P/CRE/Hygro], Promega) using Lipofectamine 2000® reagent (ThermoFisher Scientific), along with 150 ng of GPBAR1 (GPBAR1-pcDNA3.1 +/C-(K)-DYK) (Genscript, Piscataway NJ, USA) or empty vector pcDNA3.1 and 50 ng of pRL-TK *Renilla* luciferase vector (Promega). Cells were exposed to the tested ligands in the given concentrations for five hours the next day. Lipofectamine® 3000 (ThermoFisher Scientific) was used for all other transient transfection reporter gene tests. Briefly, cells were transfected with 150 ng/well luciferase reporter gene constructs (p(DR3)3-luc, p3A4-luc, pTAT-(GRE)2-TK-luc, p2B6-luc, pGL4.35 [luc2P9XGAL4UASHygro], FXRE-luc) together with 100 ng/well of the corresponding full-length fragment nuclear receptor expression vectors (pSG5-hVDR, pSG5-mFxr, pSG5-hRXR α , pSG5-hPXR, CAR3 variant) or the ligand binding domains of human pCMX-GA4L-LXR α , pCMX-GA4L-LXR α , pCMX-GA4L-TR α , pCMX-GA4L-PPAR α , pCMX-GAL4-PPAR γ , pCMX-GAL4-PPAR δ) and 30 ng/well of pRL-TK *Renilla* luciferase vector 24 h prior to the treatment as described previously [51,60]. Using the Dual Luciferase® Reporter Assay System (Promega), the firefly luciferase activity was determined and standardized to the *Renilla* luciferase activity. In reporter gene assays, the half-maximum activation (EC₅₀) and inhibition (IC₅₀) parameters of 7 β -ipCDCA were determined using GraphPad PRISM version 9.1.0 (San Diego). These values were obtained by nonlinear fitting of concentration-response curves: (log(agonist) vs. response [three parameters]) for EC₅₀ and (log(inhibitor) vs. normalized response) for IC₅₀. Every experiment was carried out in technical triplicates and has been replicated at least three times (n = 3). The fold change to control vehicle-treated (DMSO) samples is displayed for each result. All samples, including the control samples, were made using the vehicle (0.1 % DMSO).

2.12. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out using GraphPad Prism 9.1.0 software (San Diego). Data are presented as the mean representing 8–11 animals per group. Statistical significance with (p < 0.05) was determined using Ordinary one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the Holm-Sidak multiple comparisons test applied to the data if more than two groups were being analysed. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to

compare two groups. Data were excluded from analysis if they met predefined criteria, including technical errors and outliers. Points outside the whiskers of a boxplot were considered potential outliers. LC-MS data were analysed using the LipidR package in R. Briefly, lipid areas were normalized to respective class standards and log-transformed. Class enrichment was calculated by LSEA lipid enrichment analysis in the LipidR package.

3. Results

3.1. 7 β -isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid is a potent dual FXR antagonist and TGR5 agonist

In our previous study [51], we reported a BA derivative, 7 β -isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid (7 β -ipCDCA, Fig. 1a), to be a potent FXR antagonist that inhibits FXR activation induced by various synthetic and endogenous agonists, including obeticholic acid (OCA), GW4064, and chenodeoxycholic acid. Further investigation of the 7 β -ipCDCA revealed that it also antagonizes murine Fxr (mFxr) activated by 1 μ M OCA, with an IC₅₀ being 16.5 μ M (Fig. 1b). In addition, 7 β -ipCDCA activates TGR5 with an EC₅₀ being 1.4 μ M (Fig. 1c), which is similar to the activity of the potent endogenous TGR5 agonist lithocholic acid (LCA, EC₅₀ = 1.9 μ M). 7 β -ipCDCA did not exhibit any agonistic or antagonistic activity to other nuclear receptors involved in metabolic regulation including pregnane X (PXR), vitamin D (VDR), constitutive androstane (CAR), peroxisome proliferator-activated (PPAR α , γ and δ), liver X (LXR α and β), glucocorticoid (GR), and thyroid hormone (TR) receptors (Supplementary material, Figure S1).

When administered to C57BL/6 male mice by oral gavage at a dose of 10 mg/kg, we found that 7 β -ipCDCA is efficiently conjugated with taurine to form tauro-7 β -ipCDCA. This conjugate can be detected in plasma even 7 days after a single dose application (Supplementary material, Figure S2). The conjugation occurs rapidly, within 2 h post-administration, with complete conjugation of 7 β -ipCDCA, suggesting a high first-pass metabolism. Importantly, we observed that tauro-7 β -ipCDCA accumulates significantly in the intestine compared to the liver, while unconjugated 7 β -ipCDCA appears in negligible concentrations in plasma and liver tissues (Figure S2). These pharmacokinetic data indicate a predominant intestinal effect of 7 β -ipCDCA at this dose, with sufficient tissue concentrations in the intestine relative to its IC₅₀ for mFxr. Interestingly, it appears that 7 β -ipCDCA conjugates exclusively with taurine because other conjugates have not been detected in the plasma.

Since both FXR antagonism and TGR5 agonism have been proposed to improve glucose tolerance, we applied 7 β -ipCDCA to mice on a Western diet (WD). The 24-week WD significantly increased body and liver weight, but the last 6-week treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA had no effect on these parameters (Fig. 1e, f). As expected, the WD resulted in a significant increase in plasma alanine transaminase (ALT) and aspartate transaminase (AST) levels, but 7 β -ipCDCA did not further affect the plasma levels of the liver enzymes (Fig. 1g, h).

Taken together, 7 β -ipCDCA is a potent FXR antagonist/TGR5 agonist that is effectively absorbed after oral gavage and does not display any liver toxicity after 6 weeks of daily administration in mice.

3.2. 7 β -ipCDCA improves glucose tolerance and increases GLP-1 secretion in mouse on Western diet

Recent studies have discovered multiple FXR antagonists that improve disrupted glucose metabolism [13–16]. The treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) did not affect glycaemia in mice on the chow diet (C), but recovered glucose tolerance affected by WD (W) after 5 weeks of treatment (Fig. 2a, b). Importantly, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment decreased blood glucose and plasma insulin levels at the fasting state (Fig. 2c, d) in mice on WD. Insulin resistance (IR), the primary mechanism underlying diseases of glucose metabolism, is evaluated based on

Fig. 2. 7 β -ipCDCA restores glucose tolerance in mice on a Western diet. (a–e) The glucose tolerance was evaluated in fasted mice on WD for 23 weeks and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) by oral gavage for the last 5 weeks (7 mice per group). The dashed lines represent animals on the chow diet, and animals on WD are represented by plain lines. (f–h) The ipGTT was performed in mice fed WD for 23 weeks and orally gavaged with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d), OCA (10 mg/kg/d), or vehicle (1 % MC) for 7 days (6 mice per group). (i) Plasma concentration of active GLP-1 in mice on chow and WD for 21 weeks and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) by oral gavage for 7 days. After the last 7 β -ipCDCA gavage, mice were fasted for 5 h. Mice were gavaged with DPP-4 inhibitor sitagliptin (25 mg/kg) 45 min prior to the glucose (2 g/kg) bolus administration. The blood was collected by retro-orbital venipuncture after 15 min from anaesthetized animals (7 mice per group) (j) Gcg mRNA expression, encoding proglucagon precursor of GLP-1, in the ileum of mice on WD for 24 weeks and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) by oral gavage for the last 6 weeks (8–10 mice per group). (k) Gcg mRNA expression in the ileum of mice treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg) or vehicle (1 % MC) for 6 or 12 h (3–5 mice per group). Data are presented as fold change to the vehicle-treated cohort on chow diet (C) and normalized to Rplp0 mRNA expression as a reference. (l) GLP-1 secretion was measured from culture media of NCI-H716 human enterocytes treated with 7 β -ipCDCA, FSK, or LCA (all 10 μ M) for 2 h after serum starvation (3 independent experiments performed in biological triplicates). Data are shown as means \pm SD with individual values superimposed on the graphs. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001 vs. vehicle-treated mice fed chow diet (C, ##P < 0.01 vs. vehicle-treated mice on WD (W).

the diagnostic biomarker Homeostasis Model Assessment of IR (HOMA-IR). The WD doubled (mean chow 2.0 vs. WD 5.0), and treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) decreased the HOMA-IR score in mice on WD (Fig. 2e). This indicates that 7 β -ipCDCA improves the glucose metabolic alterations induced by WD.

In the next experiment, we compared the effect of 7 β -ipCDCA to the impact of the known FXR agonist OCA applied for 1 week in an *i.p.* glucose tolerance test (ipGTT) (Fig. 2f–g). Briefly, mice on WD for 23

weeks were orally gavaged with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d), OCA (10 mg/kg/d), or vehicle (1 % MC) for 1 week with simultaneous application of WD. The treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA significantly reduced, whereas OCA treatment had no effect on the time profile of glycaemia (Fig. 2f, g). Interestingly, OCA treatment led to a significant increase in the fasting blood glucose level. 7 β -ipCDCA had no impact on fasting glycaemia after 1 week of administration (Fig. 2h), while it significantly decreased fasting blood glycaemia after 5 weeks of treatment (Fig. 2c).

This might suggest that the effect of the FXR antagonist develops progressively.

In response to food consumption, the intestinal L-cells release the incretin hormone glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1), which in healthy people increases glucose-dependent insulin secretion [25]. Both intestinal FXR inhibition [18] and TGR5 activation [30,61] have been reported to enhance GLP-1 secretion from intestinal L-cells. Indeed, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment (10 mg/kg/d for 7 days by oral gavage) enhanced active GLP-1 secretion in response to glucose in mice on WD but not in mice on the chow diet (Fig. 2i). Even though we did not detect the increased expression of proglucagon (Gcg) mRNA in either condition after six weeks of treatment (Fig. 2j), we observed increased Gcg mRNA after 6 and 12 h following a single dose of 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg) in the murine ileum (Fig. 2k). This suggests rather an acute and transient regulation than a long-term effect by 7 β -ipCDCA on Gcg mRNA expression, a precursor mRNA encoding proglucagon and GLP-1. The GLP-1 secretion from NCI-H716 human enteroendocrine cells was also induced by a 2 h treatment with 10 μ M 7 β -ipCDCA, to the same extent as FSK and LCA, known TGR5 ligands (Fig. 2l).

In conclusion, the treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA significantly improved

glucose tolerance in mice on WD (Fig. 2a), likely by increasing the release of GLP-1 from enteroendocrine L cells.

3.3. 7 β -ipCDCA affects the expression of glucose transporters in the intestine and kidney but not in the liver or adipose tissue

Glucose absorption significantly impacts glycaemia. In our study, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment (10 mg/kg/d for 6 weeks) significantly decreased the expression of SglT1 and Glut2 transporters upregulated by WD in the mouse ilea (Fig. 3a, b). In addition, 7 β -ipCDCA downregulated the mRNA expression of SglT1 and Glut2 transporters in the murine enteroendocrine L cell line, GLUTag, after 10 μ M 7 β -ipCDCA treatment for 24 h. The FXR agonist OCA (10 μ M) had no effect on these glucose transporters (Fig. 3c, d).

Next, we performed the analysis of the whole transcriptome of the livers of C57BL/6 mice treated with a single dose of 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg in gavage) after 24 h. Interestingly, the effect on the hepatic metabolic genes was marginal under the experimental condition. Importantly, Cyp7a1 mRNA, the key FXR target gene, was upregulated underlying the FXR antagonistic activity of 7 β -ipCDCA *in vivo* in the

Fig. 3. 7 β -ipCDCA affects the expression of glucose transporters in the intestine but not in the liver, adipose tissue, or kidney. (a, b) The mRNA expression of glucose transporter SglT1 and Glut2 was determined in ileal samples in mice on Western or chow diet and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) for 6 weeks (8–10 mice per group). (c, d) The mRNA expression of SglT1 and Glut2 was measured in GLUTag cells treated with vehicle (0.1 % DMSO, ctrl), OCA, or 7 β -ipCDCA (both 10 μ M) for 24 h. (n = 3) (e) Clustered heatmap of differentially expressed genes in the liver of vehicle- (C) and 7 β -ipCDCA- (7 β ipCDCA, single dose 10 mg/kg) treated mice for 24 h (4 animals per group). (f) The liver, (g) kidney, and (h) white adipose tissue mRNA expression in mice on Western or chow diet and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) for 6 weeks (8–10 mice per group). Data are presented as means \pm SD with individual values superimposed on the graphs. *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001 vs. vehicle-treated cohort on chow diet in mice experiments or vs. vehicle (DMSO) treated cells, #P < 0.05 vs. vehicle-treated mice under WD.

animal experiments (Fig. 3e). In contrast to the significant effect in the ileum, treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA for six weeks did not affect the expression of glucose transporters Glut2 or Glut1 in the livers of animals on WD (Fig. 3f), but WD upregulated the expression of Glut2 mRNA. Interestingly, Glut1 mRNA was upregulated after 7 β -ipCDCA treatment in the mice cohort on the chow diet (Fig. 3f). Consistent with the Fxr antagonistic effect of 7 β -ipCDCA, Cyp7a1 mRNA expression was upregulated in mice fed WD diet, which itself increased its expression after six weeks (Fig. 3f). The expression of the gluconeogenic genes Pck1 and G6pc was decreased in the livers of animals on the WD diet, and 7 β -ipCDCA treatment had an additional significant effect on G6pc mRNA expression. Interestingly, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment also increased the mRNA levels of glucokinase (Gck), the enzyme catalyzing the first step of both glycogen synthesis and glycolysis, in the livers of mice on the chow diet (Fig. 3f).

In the kidney, the WD did not alter the expression of the glucose transporter SglT2, but the treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA led to a significant downregulation of SglT2 mRNA expression in mice on WD (Fig. 3g). Interestingly, G6pc mRNA was upregulated after 7 β -ipCDCA treatment in the mice cohort on the chow diet, whereas there was no effect in animals on WD. Similarly, we did not observe an effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on Pck1 mRNA expression in the kidney (Fig. 3g). The expression of glucose transporters Glut1 and Glut4 in the white adipose tissue (WAT) remained unchanged in all groups. However, the treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA significantly decreased the upregulated Pck1 gluconeogenic gene in the fat of mice on WD. Of note, Pck1 in the WAT is involved in glycerolneogenesis (as the key part of TG synthesis) [62]. In addition, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment attenuated the expression of G6pc mRNA in the WAT in mice under a normal diet (Fig. 3h).

Taken together, 7 β -ipCDCA inhibited the expression of SglT1 and Glut2 glucose transporters in the ileum and SglT2 in the kidney of mice fed WD. In contrast, changes in the hepatic genes regulating glucose metabolism were marginal after 7 β -ipCDCA treatment.

3.4. Effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on bile acid secretion and metabolism in mice fed a Western diet

The composition of the BA pool plays a crucial role in regulating glucose and lipid metabolism [2,63]. WD significantly increased the alkaline phosphatase (ALP) plasma concentration (Fig. 4a). In contrast, bile flow (BF) and BF to liver weight (BF/LW) were decreased in mice on WD for 24 weeks (Fig. 4b, c). The treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) for six weeks by oral gavage had no additional effect on ALP or BF. WD led to a decreased concentration of BAs in the bile, and 7 β -ipCDCA had no additional effect (Fig. 4d). WD impacted multiple target genes involved in BA transport and synthesis in the liver (including Cyp7a1, Cyp27a1, Cyp7b1, Cyp2c70, Baat, Mrp2, Mrp4, Ost β , and Ntcp). Compared to vehicle-treated mice on WD (W), 7 β -ipCDCA administration significantly increased only the expression of hepatic Cyp7a1 mRNA, the key FXR target gene (Fig. 4e).

In contrast, the FXR antagonistic property of 7 β -ipCDCA was significantly manifested in the ileum of mice treated with WD. It significantly reduced the expression of FXR target genes Shp and Fgf15 upregulated by WD (Fig. 4f-g). In addition, it decreased the expression of Fxr (Nr1h4) mRNA (Fig. 4h). WD resulted in a significantly increased mRNA expression of BA transporters Ostx and Ost β ; and the treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA significantly abrogated the upregulation of both transporters (Fig. 4i, j). No effects of the WD or 7 β -ipCDCA were observed on the mRNA expression of Asbt (Ibat, Slc10a2) transporter (Fig. 4k).

The levels of individual BA species were measured in bile, plasma, and stool in mice on WD and co-administered with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) for the last 6 weeks by oral gavage. In plasma, 7 β -ipCDCA did not significantly affect the total BA pool (Fig. 4l), but the concentration of the primary BA taurocholic acid (TCA) was significantly increased (Fig. 4m). The increase of TCA in plasma was mirrored by the increase of

total conjugated and 12-OH BAs in murine plasma after 7 β -ipCDCA administration (Fig. 4n, o). This phenomenon may be attributable to the upregulation of the Mrp4 bile acid transporter at the basolateral membrane of hepatocytes (Fig. 4e), which facilitates the efflux of BA conjugates into the blood. In the stool, WD increased the total BA content per 24 h, mainly by increasing the amount of both isoforms (α and β) of primary muricholic acid (MCA) (Fig. 4p-r). Interestingly, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment led to a significant reduction of α MCA in mice on WD (Fig. 4q).

In summary, 7 β -ipCDCA significantly antagonized the ileal FXR signalling network induced by excessive nutritional intake from WD. In the liver, the FXR antagonistic activity of 7 β -ipCDCA was underlined only by upregulated Cyp7a1 mRNA expression. Importantly, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment increased the plasma concentration of TCA.

3.5. Effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on the lipidome of mice fed a Western diet

The important role of FXR in the regulation of lipid and cholesterol metabolism was underlined in FXR-deficient animals [63]. In our experiments, the WAT weight (Fig. 5a) and plasma triacylglycerol levels (TG, Fig. 5b) increased significantly in mice on WD. Hepatic TG as well as diacylglycerides (DG) were significantly increased in mice on the chow diet treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (Fig. 5c). The effect on TG was not recapitulated by 7 β -ipCDCA treatment in mice challenged with WD. The amount of DG was modestly but significantly increased compared to the effect in mice on the chow diet (Fig. 5d). On the other hand, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment resulted in a significant increase in cholesteryl esters (CE) levels in the livers of mice on WD. Complete lipidome analysis is available in the [Supplementary material \(Figure S3\)](#). The plasma levels of total, HDL, or LDL-cholesterol were not affected by 7 β -ipCDCA treatment ([Supplementary material, Figure S4a,b,c](#)).

Mechanistically, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment had an impact on several genes involved in hepatic lipid homeostasis after a six-week treatment. First, 7 β -ipCDCA significantly upregulated the mRNA expression of Ppara (encoding Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha - PPAR- α), Pgc1a (peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha and Cpt1a (carnitine palmitoyltransferase I) in mice on WD. In addition, Pgc1a mRNA expression was also increased in mice on a chow diet and decreased by WD (Fig. 5e). Interestingly, 7 β -ipCDCA upregulated the expression of lipogenic fatty acid synthase (Fasn) in mice on the chow diet but decreased its WD-induced expression (Fig. 5f). 7 β -ipCDCA increased perilipin-2 (Plin2) mRNA expression in the liver of mice on chow but not in WD (Fig. 5g). In addition, 7 β -ipCDCA significantly increased mRNA expression of Hmgcs2 (encoding 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA synthase 2 enzyme involved in ketogenesis) and Insig1 mRNA in the liver ([Figure S4d](#)).

Taken together, the effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on the lipidome and key genes involved in lipid metabolism varied depending on the diet. 7 β -ipCDCA increased TG accumulation in the liver of animals on a chow diet. Nevertheless, this effect was not observed in the cohort on WD, likely due to increased expression of the genes involved in FA β -oxidation and the decreased expression of the lipogenic gene Fasn. In addition, 7 β -ipCDCA significantly increased cholesteryl esters in the livers of WD-fed mice.

4. Discussion

In this study, we explored the effects of 7 β -isopropylchenodeoxycholic acid (7 β -ipCDCA), a compound with the unique combination of FXR antagonism and TGR5 agonism activities, on glucose homeostasis. Both activities of 7 β -ipCDCA might contribute to its metabolic effects. Oral administration of 7 β -ipCDCA significantly improved glucose metabolism impaired by a Western diet in C57BL/6 male mice. We show that 7 β -ipCDCA targets multiple levels of glucose metabolism regulation. 7 β -ipCDCA enhanced the release of incretin GLP-1 in mice on a Western diet, a hormone crucial for regulating

Fig. 4. The FXR-antagonistic activity of 7β-ipCDCA is primarily manifested in the ileum of mice on Western diet. (a) The concentration of ALP in the plasma (b, c) bile flow (BF) and BF to liver weight (LW); (d) amount of BAs secreted into the bile; (e) hepatic mRNA expression of genes involved in BA transport and synthesis; and (f-k) ileal gene expression. (l-o) Plasma (p-s) and stool BA concentration and amounts eliminated per 24 h in mice fed WD for 24 weeks and administered with 7β-ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) for six weeks by oral gavage. Data are presented as means ± SD with individual values superimposed on the graphs (8–10 mice per group). Asterisk (*) denotes for statistically significant difference to vehicle-treated mice on the chow diet (*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001) and hashtag (#) represents statistically significant difference to vehicle-treated mice on WD (#P < 0.05, ##P < 0.01, ###P < 0.001).

Fig. 5. 7 β -ipCDCA affects lipid metabolism differently in mice on chow and Western diets. (a) The white adipose tissue (WAT) weight and (b) plasma triacylglycerols (TG) levels were determined in mice fed chow or WD for 25 weeks and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) by oral gavage for last 6 weeks (8–10 mice per group) (c,d). The hepatic lipidome was analysed in liver tissue samples in mice on a chow (c) or a Western (d) diet. TG denotes triacylglycerols, SM sphingomyelins, PS phosphatidylserines, PC phosphatidylcholines, LPC lysophosphatidylcholines, DG diglycerides, Cer ceramides, CE cholesteryl esters. Data are presented as log₂ fold changes of lipid compounds between the 7 β -ipCDCA-treated group and the control group, with means that were either statistically significant (blue) or insignificant (black), based on LSEA, $n = 4$ per group. (e–g) mRNA expression in the liver of mice fed chow or WD for 24 weeks and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA (10 mg/kg/d) or vehicle (1 % MC) by oral gavage for the last 6 weeks. Data are presented as means \pm SD with individual values superimposed on the graphs (8–10 mice per group). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$, vs. vehicle-treated chow diet (C), # $P < 0.05$, ### $P < 0.001$ vs. vehicle-treated mice under WD (W).

insulin secretion and glucose homeostasis in diabetic contexts. Furthermore, to our knowledge, this is the first report demonstrating the effect of an FXR antagonist on glucose transporters Sglt1 and Glut2 in the murine ileum, as well as Sglt2 in the kidneys.

Both the intestinal FXR inhibition and TGR5 activation have been shown to increase the capability of L cells to produce and secrete GLP-1. This dual-target strategy has been encouraged by previous research as a promising approach for diabetes treatment [18,64]. Recent studies suggest that GLP-1 also mediates the metabolic effects of metformin, gut microbiota, and bariatric surgery [11,30,65,66]. In our work, we showed that 7 β -ipCDCA significantly upregulates proglucagon Gcg mRNA in the ileum of mice after 6 and 12 h of treatment (Fig. 2k) and in NCI-H716 enteroendocrine L cells (Fig. 2i). The effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on plasma GLP-1 level in mice fed WD and treated with 7 β -ipCDCA was on the border of statistical significance (Fig. 2i).

The intestinal expression of SGLT1 transporter [44,45,47] is increased in the experimental models of diabetes and patients with T2DM or obesity [46,67], highlighting its potential as a therapeutic target. The role of FXR in regulating this transporter's function has been poorly investigated to date. Here, we show that FXR antagonist 7 β -ipCDCA significantly decreased the ileal Sglt1 mRNA expression (Fig. 3a), potentially contributing to reduced glucose absorption, providing a potential mechanism for its effect on glucose homeostasis. Indeed, the recent use of selective SGLT1 or dual SGLT1/SGLT2 inhibitors was shown to reduce postprandial blood glucose levels and improve metabolic parameters in T2DM patients without serious gastrointestinal side effects [68–70]. Importantly, 7 β -ipCDCA also attenuated the expression of the kidney SGLT2 transporter in mice on a Western diet. A recent meta-analysis confirmed a beneficial effect of SGLT2 inhibitors in MASH patients, particularly in patients with

coexisting T2DM [71].

Increased GLUT2 expression [42,43] and incorporation into the apical membrane have been linked to obesity, insulin sensitivity, and the development of diabetes [72]. In addition, the absence of functional GLUT2 has been shown to improve metabolic and gut homeostasis in the intestine by mimicking caloric restriction [73]. In our study, 7 β -ipCDCA downregulates the increased expression of Glut2 mRNA exclusively in the ileum in mice fed a Western diet (Fig. 3b).

FXR antagonists have been shown to attenuate gluconeogenesis (compound HS218) [17] with a concomitant increase in glycogen synthesis in the liver (in the case of mebhdrolin) [15]. We did not see any effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on hepatic Pck1 mRNA expression, but G6pc mRNA expression was significantly downregulated by 7 β -ipCDCA in mice fed a WD (Fig. 3 f). However, these FXR antagonists have different molecular mechanisms. HS218 inhibits FXR binding to PGC-1 α [17], whereas mebhdrolin acts via the miR-22-3p signalling pathway [15]. This might be explained by differential conformational changes upon binding to the ligand-binding domain of FXR. We previously showed that recruitment of 7 β -ipCDCA to the FXR ligand binding domain is associated with destabilization of the α AF-2 region that inhibits both co-activator and co-repressor recruitment [74].

Increased stool BA accumulation significantly enhanced ileal FXR signalling in the mice fed an HFD (Fig. 4f–k). 7 β -ipCDCA treatment led to a significant suppression of intestinal FXR signalling, whereas its effect in the liver was less pronounced (Fig. 4e–j). In the liver, 7 β -ipCDCA administration increased Cyp7a1 mRNA expression, likely due to reduced Fgf15 signalling from the intestine, which is known to inhibit Cyp7a1 mRNA expression [75]. On the other hand, Cyp8b1, which is primarily regulated via the hepatic Fxr-Shp axis [76], remained unchanged after 7 β -ipCDCA treatment. Taken together, this indicates a

dominant role of 7 β -ipCDCA in the intestine, but not in the liver. Notably, 7 β -ipCDCA did not affect bile flow nor the BA pool in the bile in mice on WD. Nevertheless, the treatment with 7 β -ipCDCA increased TCA levels in the plasma, which may enhance TGR5 signaling and, in turn, potentially improve glucose homeostasis by promoting GLP-1 release [77].

Previous studies in FXR-deficient mice have shown that FXR is essential for lipid homeostasis and glucose regulation under normal dietary conditions, with its absence leading to metabolic dysfunction [78]. Interestingly, FXR-deficient mice appear protected from metabolic disturbances induced by a high-fat diet, such as steatosis and dyslipidemia [63,79]. This suggests that the loss of FXR may alter the liver's response to dietary fats and help maintain metabolic stability under dietary stress. According to these findings, we observed different effects of FXR antagonism by 7 β -ipCDCA in mice fed chow or WD. In chow-fed mice, 7 β -ipCDCA treatment significantly raised liver TG and DG levels, indicating that FXR activation promotes lipid accumulation in the livers of mice under standard dietary conditions. However, in mice on a Western diet, the effect of 7 β -ipCDCA on liver TG accumulation was not as pronounced, and only modest increases in DG were observed (Fig. 5c, d), suggesting a reduced response to FXR activation under high-fat diet conditions. At the molecular level, 7 β -ipCDCA upregulated genes involved in hepatic fatty acid β -oxidation (Ppara, Pgc1a, Cpt1a) in Western diet-fed mice. In contrast, the lipogenic gene Fasn mRNA was upregulated in chow-fed mice but downregulated in those on a Western diet (Fig. 5e,f). This highlights the complex interplay between FXR signalling and nutritional state, suggesting that FXR adapts liver metabolism based on dietary substrates, with its activity shifting in response to overnutrition. A limitation to the generalisability of the study is that it did not consider gender/sex issues.

Taken together, our findings highlight the potential of 7 β -ipCDCA as a novel experimental tool and potential therapeutic approach in metabolic conditions characterized by disturbed glucose homeostasis, such as T2DM. By simultaneously antagonizing FXR and activating TGR5, 7 β -ipCDCA offers a multi-faceted mechanism of action that may overcome the limitations of current therapies.

5. Author contributions

A.S., Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Roles/Writing - original draft; K.D., Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; H.L., Investigation; Methodology; J.S., Investigation; Data curation; M.B., Investigation; Methodology; S.L., Methodology; Resources; V.T., Investigation; Methodology; M.K., Investigation; E.K., Resources; Writing - review & editing; M.H., Investigation; Methodology; O.K., Resources; Validation; Writing - review & editing; S.M., Resources; Validation; Writing - review & editing; P.P., Conceptualization; Resources; Project administration; Validation; Writing - review & editing.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Milos Hroch: Investigation. **Eva Kudova:** Investigation. **Miroslav Kaspar:** Investigation. **Veronique Touche:** Investigation, Conceptualization. **Hana Lastuvkova:** Investigation. **Klara Dohnalova:** Methodology, Investigation. **Otto Kucera:** Methodology, Investigation. **Alzbeta Stefela:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stanislav Micuda:** Investigation, Conceptualization. **Petr Pavlek:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sophie Lestavel:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Maria Bajnokova:** Methodology, Investigation. **Josef Skoda:** Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used the Grammarly AI Writing assistance tool in order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Funding

The project is funded by the New Technologies for Translational Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences (NETPHARM) project (ID CZ.02.01.01/00/22-008/0004607), co-funded by the European Union. This project was also supported by the Czech Academy of Sciences institutional support (RVO:61388963) and student SVV project (No. 260 663) to M.B.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Prof. Petr Pavlek is a consultant in LipideraTherapeutics. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We want to thank our assistants, Kristyna Trubacova and Dagmar Jezkova for their excellent technical support. Alzbeta Stefela is grateful for the financial support of the Martina Roeselova Memorial Fellowship granted by the IOCB Tech Foundation.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.phrs.2025.107950.

Data availability

Transcriptome – NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus database under the GEO Series accession number GSE291059.

Bile acid metabolomics and lipidomics datasets -FigShare DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.28938395 <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28938395.v1>

References

- [1] B.L. Copple, T. Li, Pharmacology of bile acid receptors: evolution of bile acids from simple detergents to complex signaling molecules, *Pharm. Res.* 104 (2016) 9–21.
- [2] S. Lazarević, et al., Semisynthetic bile acids: a new therapeutic option for metabolic syndrome, *Pharm. Res.* 146 (2019) 104333.
- [3] C.J. Sinal, et al., Targeted disruption of the nuclear receptor FXR/BAR impairs bile acid and lipid homeostasis, *Cell* 102 (6) (2000) 731–744.
- [4] J. Prawitt, et al., Farnesoid x receptor deficiency improves glucose homeostasis in mouse models of obesity, *Diabetes* 60 (7) (2011) 1861–1871.
- [5] Y. Zhang, et al., Loss of FXR protects against diet-induced obesity and accelerates liver carcinogenesis in Ob/Ob mice, *Mol. Endocrinol.* 26 (2) (2012) 272–280.
- [6] F. Li, et al., Microbiome remodelling leads to inhibition of intestinal farnesoid x receptor signalling and decreased obesity, *Nat. Commun.* 4 (2013) 2384.
- [7] S. Fang, et al., Intestinal FXR agonism promotes adipose tissue browning and reduces obesity and insulin resistance, *Nat. Med.* 21 (2) (2015) 159–165.
- [8] Y. Zhang, et al., Activation of the nuclear receptor FXR improves hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia in diabetic mice, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 103 (4) (2006) 1006–1011.
- [9] M. Watanabe, et al., Lowering bile acid pool size with a synthetic farnesoid x receptor (FXR) agonist induces obesity and diabetes through reduced energy expenditure, *J. Biol. Chem.* 286 (30) (2011) 26913–26920.
- [10] C. Xie, et al., An intestinal farnesoid x Receptor-Ceramide signaling axis modulates hepatic gluconeogenesis in mice, *Diabetes* 66 (3) (2017) 613–626.

- [11] L. Sun, et al., Gut microbiota and intestinal FXR mediate the clinical benefits of metformin, *Nat. Med.* 24 (12) (2018) 1919–1929.
- [12] M. Meissner, et al., Bile acid sequestration reduces plasma glucose levels in db/db mice by increasing its metabolic clearance rate, *PLoS One* 6 (11) (2011) e24564.
- [13] C. Zhang, et al., Discovery of betulinic acid derivatives as potent intestinal farnesoid x receptor antagonists to ameliorate nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, *J. Med. Chem.* 65 (19) (2022) 13452–13472.
- [14] T. Sasaki, et al., Sesamin and hepatic metabolites derived from sesamin and episesamin antagonize farnesoid x receptor and reduce the expression of Gluconeogenesis-Related genes, *J. Nutr. Sci. Vitam.* 68 (1) (2022) 55–64.
- [15] T. Zhao, et al., Mebhydrolin ameliorates glucose homeostasis in type 2 diabetic mice by functioning as a selective FXR antagonist, *Metabolism* 119 (2021) 154771.
- [16] S. Wang, et al., Discovery of 12 β -oxygenated oleanolic acid alkyl esters as potent and selective FXR modulators exhibiting hyperglycemia amelioration in vivo, *Bioorg. Chem.* 129 (2022) 106203.
- [17] X. Xu, et al., HS218 as an FXR antagonist suppresses gluconeogenesis by inhibiting FXR binding to PGC-1 α promoter, *Metabolism* 85 (2018) 126–138.
- [18] M.S. Trabelsi, et al., Farnesoid x receptor inhibits glucagon-like peptide-1 production by enteroendocrine I cells, *Nat. Commun.* 6 (2015) 7629.
- [19] S. Ducastel, et al., The nuclear receptor FXR inhibits Glucagon-Like Peptide-1 secretion in response to microbiota-derived Short-Chain fatty acids, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1) (2020) 174.
- [20] L.L. Baggio, D.J. Drucker, Biology of incretins: GLP-1 and GIP, *Gastroenterology* 132 (6) (2007) 2131–2157.
- [21] M.J. Davies, C. Bianchi, S. Del Prato, Use of incretin-based medications: what do current international recommendations suggest with respect to GLP-1 receptor agonists and DPP-4 inhibitors? *Metabolism* 107 (2020) 154242.
- [22] P. Yadav, et al., Glucagon-like peptide 1 and fibroblast growth factor-21 in non-alcoholic steatohepatitis: an experimental to clinical perspective, *Pharm. Res.* 184 (2022) 106426.
- [23] C.H. Zhang, et al., Molecular mechanisms of hepatic insulin resistance in nonalcoholic fatty liver disease and potential treatment strategies, *Pharm. Res.* 159 (2020) 104984.
- [24] Y. Yan, et al., Hepatic thyroid hormone signalling modulates glucose homeostasis through the regulation of GLP-1 production via bile acid-mediated FXR antagonism, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (1) (2022) 6408.
- [25] Kuhre, R.E., et al., What Is an L-Cell and How Do We Study the Secretory Mechanisms of the L-Cell? *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2021. 12: p. 694284.
- [26] W. Jin, et al., Update on the development of TGR5 agonists for human diseases, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 271 (2024) 116462.
- [27] Y. Yun, et al., Identification of betulinic acid derivatives as potent TGR5 agonists with antidiabetic effects via humanized TGR5(H88Y) mutant mice, *J. Med. Chem.* 64 (16) (2021) 12181–12199.
- [28] T. Sasaki, et al., Muscle-specific TGR5 overexpression improves glucose clearance in glucose-intolerant mice, *J. Biol. Chem.* 296 (2021) 100131.
- [29] S. Huang, et al., TGR5 agonist ameliorates insulin resistance in the skeletal muscles and improves glucose homeostasis in diabetic mice, *Metabolism* 99 (2019) 45–56.
- [30] S.N. Chaudhari, et al., Bariatric surgery reveals a gut-restricted TGR5 agonist with anti-diabetic effects, *Nat. Chem. Biol.* 17 (1) (2021) 20–29.
- [31] J. Gillard, et al., Enterohepatic takeda G-Protein coupled receptor 5 agonism in metabolic Dysfunction-Associated fatty liver disease and related glucose dysmetabolism, *Nutrients* 14 (13) (2022).
- [32] Y. Yang, et al., Finger citron extract ameliorates glycolipid metabolism and inflammation by regulating GLP-1 secretion via TGR5 receptors in obese rats, *Evid. Based Complement Altern. Med.* 2021 (2021) 6623379.
- [33] L.S. Jiang, et al., Ginsenoside ro ameliorates High-Fat Diet-Induced obesity and insulin resistance in mice via activation of the g Protein-Coupled bile acid receptor 5 pathway, *J. Pharm. Exp. Ther.* 377 (3) (2021) 441–451.
- [34] G. Calderon, et al., Ileo-colonic delivery of conjugated bile acids improves glucose homeostasis via colonic GLP-1-producing enteroendocrine cells in human obesity and diabetes, *EBioMedicine* 55 (2020) 102759.
- [35] X.P. Bai, et al., Influence of ursodeoxycholic acid on blood glucose, insulin and GLP-1 in rats with liver fibrosis induced by bile duct ligation, *Diabetol. Metab. Syndr.* 15 (1) (2023) 18.
- [36] F. Tian, et al., Compound k attenuates hyperglycemia by enhancing glucagon-like peptide-1 secretion through activating TGR5 via the remodeling of gut microbiota and bile acid metabolism, *J. Ginseng Res.* 46 (6) (2022) 780–789.
- [37] K. Makkı, et al., 6 α -hydroxylated bile acids mediate TGR5 signalling to improve glucose metabolism upon dietary fiber supplementation in mice, *Gut* 72 (2) (2023) 314–324.
- [38] J. Münzker, et al., Functional changes of the gastric bypass microbiota reactivate thermogenic adipose tissue and systemic glucose control via intestinal FXR-TGR5 crosstalk in diet-induced obesity, *Microbiome* 10 (1) (2022) 96.
- [39] L.V. Gromova, S.O. Fetisov, A.A. Gruzdkov, Mechanisms of glucose absorption in the small intestine in health and metabolic diseases and their role in appetite regulation, *Nutrients* 13 (7) (2021).
- [40] B. Merino, et al., Intestinal fructose and glucose metabolism in health and disease, *Nutrients* 12 (1) (2019).
- [41] H. Koepsell, Glucose transporters in the small intestine in health and disease, *Pflug. Arch.* 472 (9) (2020) 1207–1248.
- [42] V. Tobin, et al., Insulin internalizes GLUT2 in the enterocytes of healthy but not insulin-resistant mice, *Diabetes* 57 (3) (2008) 555–562.
- [43] A. Ait-Omar, et al., GLUT2 accumulation in enterocyte apical and intracellular membranes: a study in morbidly obese human subjects and Ob/Ob and high fat-fed mice, *Diabetes* 60 (10) (2011) 2598–2607.
- [44] H. Ogata, et al., KATP channel as well as SGLT1 participates in GIP secretion in the diabetic state, *J. Endocrinol.* 222 (2) (2014) 191–200.
- [45] Y. Fujita, et al., Increased intestinal glucose absorption and postprandial hyperglycaemia at the early step of glucose intolerance in otsuka Long-Evans tokushima fatty rats, *Diabetologia* 41 (12) (1998) 1459–1466.
- [46] J. Dyer, et al., Expression of monosaccharide transporters in intestine of diabetic humans, *Am. J. Physiol. Gastrointest. Liver Physiol.* 282 (2) (2002) G241–G248.
- [47] P. Song, et al., Sodium glucose cotransporter SGLT1 as a therapeutic target in diabetes mellitus, *Expert Opin. Ther. Targets* 20 (9) (2016) 1109–1125.
- [48] L. Zubiaga, et al., Oral metformin transiently lowers post-prandial glucose response by reducing the apical expression of sodium-glucose co-transporter 1 in enterocytes, *iScience* 26 (4) (2023) 106057.
- [49] L. Li, et al., FXR activation alleviates tacrolimus-induced post-transplant diabetes mellitus by regulating renal gluconeogenesis and glucose uptake, *J. Transl. Med.* 17 (1) (2019) 418.
- [50] L. Zhao, et al., A novel role for farnesoid x receptor in the bile acid-mediated intestinal glucose homeostasis, *J. Cell Mol. Med.* 24 (21) (2020) 12848–12861.
- [51] A. Stefela, E)-7-Ethylidene-lithocholic acid (7-ELCA) is a potent dual farnesoid x receptor (FXR) antagonist and GPBAR1 agonist inhibiting FXR-Induced gene expression in hepatocytes and stimulating Glucagon-like Peptide-1 secretion from enteroendocrine cells 12 *Front Pharm.* 2021, 713149.
- [52] M. Ganz, T. Csak, G. Szabo, High fat diet feeding results in gender specific steatohepatitis and inflammasome activation, *World J. Gastroenterol.* 20 (26) (2014) 8525–8534.
- [53] H. Lastuvkova, et al., Dimethyl fumarate attenuates bile acid retention and liver fibrosis in a mouse model of cholestasis, *Am. J. Physiol. Gastrointest. Liver Physiol.* 328 (5) (2025) G558–g577.
- [54] M. Uher, et al., An alternative approach to validation of liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry methods for the quantification of endogenous compounds, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1705 (2023) 464173.
- [55] H. Lastuvkova, et al., Carvedilol impairs bile acid homeostasis in mice: implication for nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, *Toxicol. Sci.* 196 (2) (2023) 200–217.
- [56] S. Picon, et al., Discovery, Structure-Activity relationships, and in vivo activity of dihydropyridone agonists of the bile acid receptor TGR5, *J. Med. Chem.* 66 (17) (2023) 11732–11760.
- [57] A. Stefela, et al., 3 β -Isoobeticolic acid efficiently activates the farnesoid x receptor (FXR) due to its epimerization to 3 α -epimer by hepatic metabolism, *J. Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 202 (2020) 105702.
- [58] J. Dusek, et al., The hypolipidemic effect of MI-883, the combined CAR agonist/PXR antagonist, in diet-induced hypercholesterolemia model, *Nat. Commun.* 16 (1) (2025) 1418.
- [59] M.I. Love, W. Huber, S. Anders, Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2, *Genome Biol.* 15 (12) (2014) 550.
- [60] I. Mejdrová, et al., Discovery of novel human constitutive androstane receptor agonists with the Imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine structure, *J. Med. Chem.* 66 (4) (2023) 2422–2456.
- [61] C. Thomas, et al., TGR5-mediated bile acid sensing controls glucose homeostasis, *Cell Metab.* 10 (3) (2009) 167–177.
- [62] S. Yu, et al., Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase in cell metabolism: roles and mechanisms beyond gluconeogenesis, *Mol. Metab.* 53 (2021) 101257.
- [63] Y. Zhu, F. Li, G.L. Guo, Tissue-specific function of farnesoid x receptor in liver and intestine, *Pharm. Res.* 63 (4) (2011) 259–265.
- [64] L. Ding, et al., Notoginsenoside F1 acts as a TGR5 agonist but FXR antagonist to alleviate high fat diet-induced obesity and insulin resistance in mice, *Acta Pharm. Sin. B* 11 (6) (2021) 1541–1554.
- [65] P.V. Bauer, et al., Metformin alters upper small intestinal microbiota that impact a Glucose-SGLT1-Sensing glucoregulatory pathway, *Cell Metab.* 27 (1) (2018) 101–117.e5.
- [66] A. Wichmann, et al., Microbial modulation of energy availability in the colon regulates intestinal transit, *Cell Host Microbe* 14 (5) (2013) 582–590.
- [67] N.Q. Nguyen, et al., Accelerated intestinal glucose absorption in morbidly obese humans: relationship to glucose transporters, incretin hormones, and glycemia, *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.* 100 (3) (2015) 968–976.
- [68] C.M.A. Cefalo, et al., Sotagliflozin, the first dual SGLT inhibitor: current outlook and perspectives, *Cardiovasc Diabetol.* 18 (1) (2019) 20.
- [69] B. Zambrowicz, et al., LX4211, a dual SGLT1/SGLT2 inhibitor, improved glycemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes in a randomized, placebo-controlled trial, *Clin. Pharm. Ther.* 92 (2) (2012) 158–169.
- [70] D.R. Powell, et al., LX4211 increases serum glucagon-like peptide 1 and peptide YY levels by reducing sodium/glucose cotransporter 1 (SGLT1)-mediated absorption of intestinal glucose, *J. Pharm. Exp. Ther.* 345 (2) (2013) 250–259.
- [71] H. Li, et al., The efficacy of sodium-glucose transporter 2 inhibitors in patients with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis, *Pharm. Res.* 213 (2025) 107647.
- [72] B. Sun, et al., The role of GLUT2 in glucose metabolism in multiple organs and tissues, *Mol. Biol. Rep.* 50 (8) (2023) 6963–6974.
- [73] C.C. Schmitt, et al., Intestinal inactivation of the glucose transporter GLUT2 delays tissue distribution of glucose and reveals an unexpected role in gut homeostasis, *Mol. Metab.* 6 (1) (2017) 61–72.
- [74] A. Díaz-Holguín, et al., When two become one: conformational changes in FXR/RXR heterodimers bound to steroidal antagonists, *ChemMedChem* 18 (4) (2023) e202200556.
- [75] L. Adorini, M. Trauner, FXR agonists in NASH treatment, *J. Hepatol.* 79 (5) (2023) 1317–1331.
- [76] I. Kim, et al., Differential regulation of bile acid homeostasis by the farnesoid x receptor in liver and intestine, *J. Lipid Res.* 48 (12) (2007) 2664–2672.

- [77] C.A. Brighton, et al., Bile acids trigger GLP-1 release predominantly by accessing basolaterally located g protein-coupled bile acid receptors, *Endocrinology* 156 (11) (2015) 3961–3970.
- [78] M. Bjursell, et al., Ageing fxr deficient mice develop increased energy expenditure, improved glucose control and liver damage resembling NASH, *PLOS One* 8 (5) (2013) e64721.
- [79] W. Deng, et al., Farnesoid x receptor deficiency induces hepatic lipid and glucose metabolism disorder via regulation of pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase 4, *Oxid. Med. Cell Longev.* 2022 (2022) 3589525.